

Study on Surgery of the Tumors in the Ventricular System

Himanshu Kumar¹, Deepak Bandlish², A. K. Chaudhuri³

¹Mch Resident, Department of Neurosurgery, Bangur Institute of Neurosciences, IPGMER, Kolkata.

²Mch Resident, Department of Neurosurgery, Bangur Institute of Neurosciences, IPGMER, Kolkata.

³Professor, Department of Neurosurgery, Bangur Institute of Neurosciences, IPGMER, Kolkata.

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Corresponding author: Dr Himanshu Kumar

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Abstract

Background: This area may be affected by various tumours. The clinical aspects include mental and visual problems, as well as signs of gradually increasing or intermittently elevated intracranial pressure. Due to their placement in relation to the crucial tissues surrounding the tumour, surgical treatment of ventricular tumours is frequently difficult to have a successful surgical outcome. study of the surgical results and clinical manifestations of ventricular system malignancies.

Methods: The research involved 15 patients with ventricular tumours. Analysis was done on the clinical presentation, radiological findings, several surgical techniques, and outcome. Based on where they were found during an MRI, tumours were divided into three groups: lateral, third, and fourth ventricles. Transcortical approach, transcallosal approach, median suboccipital approach, and subfrontal approach were used during surgery on eight patients each. In 10 individuals, the gross complete removal was accomplished. The rest underwent partial resections. The surgical outcome was assessed using the Glasgow outcome scale.

Results: The most common clinical manifestations included sudden onset of headache and altered level of consciousness in patients with tumours in the third and fourth ventricles, as well as chronic headache in individuals with tumours in the lateral ventricle. Patients with malignancies in the third ventricle were more likely to develop hydrocephalus. Postoperatively, 73% of patients had positive results (Glasgow outcome scale IV, V), while patients with tumours in the lateral ventricular tumour had better outcomes. Despite the lack of statistical validity, the differences in result according to surgical method were not detected.

Conclusion: Postoperative results for ventricular tumour patients who experience abrupt headache onset, hydrocephalus, or high grade tumour are not favourable. Patients who have tumours in the lateral ventricle generally have positive outcomes. Depending on how the tumours are approached, the results are the same. In order to prevent neurological problems, it is also important to be informed of the various approach techniques to the tumours and the architecture surrounding the ventricle.

Keywords: Tumor, Ventricle.

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Introduction

The incidence of intraventricular tumours, which account for 3 to 10 percent of all brain cancers, is remarkably low. This area may be affected by various tumours. The clinical aspects include mental and visual problems, as well as signs of gradually increasing or intermittently elevated intracranial pressure. Due to their placement in relation to the crucial tissues surrounding the tumour, surgical treatment of ventricular tumours is frequently difficult to have a successful surgical outcome. Therefore, to prevent difficulties following surgery, a correct understanding of anatomical features and neuronal processes around the ventricles is required. And the secret to a successful surgical excision of the tumour is a strategy that has been properly thought out and prepared. The clinical and radiological characteristics, surgical results, and consequences on the study in 15 patients with ventricular tumour are presented by the authors.

Materials and Methods

Who received care in the Neurosurgery division of the Bangur Institute of Neurosciences, IPGMER, Kolkata, West Bengal, between January 2013 and January 2015 were retrospectively examined. Data from the archives were used to assess the clinical presentation, radiological findings, surgical methods, pathologic findings, and results. 307 intracranial tumours were surgically removed, and 15 of these were intraventricular tumours. Based on their positions in the ventricles on an MRI, tumours were divided into three groups: lateral ventricle, third ventricle, and fourth ventricle. Transcortical approach, transcallosal approach, median suboccipital approach, and subfrontal approach were used during surgery on eight patients each. In 10 individuals, the gross complete removal was accomplished.

The rest underwent partial resections. Eight of ten patients with hydrocephalus had extraventricular cerebrospinal fluid draining prior to tumour excision.

After the tumour was removed to address the permanent hydrocephalus, there was no ventriculo-peritoneal shunt.

The follow-up time was between 8 and 57 months (mean: 25 months). Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis test were employed statistically.

Results

1:1.14 was the male to female ratio. Ages ranged from three to sixty-one (mean: 30 years old). The authors were unable to draw any conclusive conclusions about how sex and age related to the tumours.

The lateral ventricle (6 patients, 40%), the third ventricle (7 patients, 47%), and the fourth ventricle (2 patients, 13%) all saw tumour growth. The lateral ventricle and the third ventricle were the sites of the majority of tumours. Four of the six individuals with lateral ventricular tumours were in the right lateral ventricle and two were in the left.

Variable symptoms were present (Table 1). The most typical manifestation was an elevated intracranial pressure-related symptom. Major clinical symptoms included headache (10 patients, 66%), mental change (5 patients), vomiting (3 patients), vision deficiency (3 patients), seizure attack (2 patients), abnormal gait (1), memory disruption (1), and difficulty urinating (1 patient). The length of the symptoms ranged widely, from 1 day to 5 months. Patients with tumours in the lateral ventricle presented with a chronic headache that lasted for several months. Four of the seven patients with tumours in the third ventricle and one of the two patients with tumours in the fourth ventricle both experienced an acute headache along with a change in consciousness. Patients with acute symptoms frequently lost

consciousness (5 cases), and surgery had a dismal outcome with two patients dying and one going into a vegetative state. Adiposity and episodes of hypersomnia were two symptoms of a hypothalamic syndrome in a patient who had a tumour in the third

ventricle. Many lateral ventricular tumour patients' complaints were sporadic or short-lived, which delayed the diagnosis. Before the tumours start to cause symptoms, they frequently develop slowly and reach a large size.

Table 1: Clinical manifestations of patients

	Tumor locations			Total
	Lateral	Third	Fourth	
Headache	6	3	1	10
Decreased visual field	1	1	0	2
Change of mentality	0	4	0	4
Seizure	1	0	1	2
Vomiting	0	3	1	4
Gait disturbance	0	1	0	1
Incontinence	0	1	0	1
Memory disturbance	0	1	0	1
Hypersomnia	0	1	0	1

Every patient underwent an MRI before surgery. The tumours ranged in size from 1.7 cm to 9 cm (average: 4.8cm). The tumours displayed a range of signals. Given the proper tumour location and age group⁶, several neoplasms exhibit distinctive MRI features that may support the diagnosis. In our cases, MR signal intensity patterns were ineffective at predicting tumour histology. In three of six patients with a tumour in the lateral ventricle, in six of seven patients with a tumour in the third ventricle, and in one of two patients with a tumour in the fourth ventricle, hydrocephalus developed.

Different surgical techniques were applied. The meticulous investigation of imagings, particularly the arterial, venous anatomy and eloquent brain area, is what determines the surgical trajectory. In eight patients, a

transcortical technique was used via the superior parietal lobule or middle frontal gyrus.

In four cases, a transcallosal technique was used. One of them used a subfrontal translamina terminalis technique. Two patients had suboccipital approaches made. Five of the six patients with lateral ventricle tumours underwent a transcortical approach, while one underwent a transcallosal approach.

Three transcallosal interforaminal approaches, three transcortical transforaminal approaches, and one subfrontal route were used to remove the tumour from seven patients with third ventricle tumours. A suboccipital technique was used on individuals who had tumours in their fourth ventricle (Table 2).

Table 2: Surgical approaches to variety of ventricular tumors and postoperative outcome

	Tumor locations			Total
	Lateral	Third	Fourth	
Interhemispheric transcallosal	GOS 5(1)	GOS 3(1) GOS 4(1)	(0)	GOS 3(1) GOS 4(1)

		GOS 5(1)		GOS 5(1)
Transcortical transventricular	GOS 4(1) GOS 5(4)	GOS 2(1) GOS 5(2)	(0)	GOS 2(1) GOS 4(1) GOS 5(6)
Subfrontal translamina terminalis	(0)	GOS 1(1)	(0)	GOS 1(1)
Suboccipital transvermion	(0)	(0)	GOS 1(1) GOS 4(1)	GOS 1(1) GOS 4(1)

GOS: Glasgow outcome scale, GOS 5 : good recovery, GOS 4 : moderate disability (disabled but independent), GOS 3 : severe disability (conscious but disabled), GOS 2 : persistent vegetative state, GOS 1 : death (number), no. of cases

Gross-total resection was done in 12 patients, and subtotal resection in three patients. Extraventricular drainage of the cerebrospinal fluid was executed in eight of 10 patients with hydrocephalus before tumor mass removal. There, however, were no patients with ventriculo-peritoneal shunt for the treatment of the permanent hydrocephalus after surgery.

Surgical outcome was classified with Glasgow outcome Scale (GOS). It showed good recovery (GR) in eight (53%), moderate disability (MD) in three (20%), severe disability (SD) in one (7%), vegetative state (VS) in one (7%), death (D) in two (13%). Surgical outcome was relatively good in 11 patients with good recovery and moderate disability (73%) (Table 2).

Patients with tumours in the lateral ventricle had surgical outcomes that were 4 and 5 points better than those of other groups, according to the Glasgow outcome scale. Three of the five patients who had mental decline before to surgery exhibited unsatisfactory outcomes. Two of these three patients passed away from tumour recurrence, and the third patient was in a vegetative state. The recurrent patients'

histological diagnoses included pilocytic astrocytoma, anaplastic astrocytoma, and atypical teratoid-rhabdoid tumour.

Central neurocytomas (2 instances), meningiomas (2 cases), subependymal giant cell astrocytomas (1 case), and germinomas were the tumours found in the lateral ventricle (1 case). One case each of chordoid astrocytoma, paragonimiasis, pilocytic astrocytoma, metastatic tumour, germinoma, anaplastic astrocytoma, and neuroepithelial cyst made up the third ventricle cancers (1 case). Atypical teratoid-rhabdoid tumour and primitive neuroectodermal tumour were the two types of tumours found in the fourth ventricle (Table 4). Due to a lack of patients for data, it was challenging to determine the ventricle's preferred place for tumour growth.

Meningitis struck two patients, transient hemiparesis struck two, transient dysarthria struck one, subdural hygroma struck one, CSF leakage struck one, truncal ataxia struck one, central diabetes insipidus struck one, ptosis struck one, gait disturbance struck one, and eyeball deviation struck one among the postoperative complications (Table 3). The majority of neurologic problems were brief and resolved in three to nine months.

Table 3: Postoperative complications of patients

	Tumor locations			Total
	Lateral	Third	Fourth	
CSF leakage	1	0	0	1
Hemiparesis	1	1	0	2

Eyeball deviation	0	0	1	1
Ataxia	0	0	1	1
Dysarthria	1	0	1	2
Central diabetes insipidus	1	0	0	1
Ptosis	0	1	0	1
Gall disturbance	0	1	0	1
Meningitis	1	1	0	2
Subdural hygroma	0	1	0	1

Table 4: Histopathologic findings of the tumors

	Tumor locations			Total
	Lateral	Third	Fourth	
Meningioma	2	0	0	2
Germinoma	1	1	0	2
Central neurocytoma	2	0	0	2
Chordoid astrocytoma	0	1	0	1
Pilocytic astrocytoma	0	1	0	1
Anaplastic astrocytoma	0	1	0	1
Subependymal giant cell tumor	1	0	0	1
Primitive neuroectodermal tumor	0	0	1	1
Atypical teratoid-rhabdoid tumor	0	0	1	1
Metastatic tumor	0	1	0	1
Neuroepithelial cyst	0	1	0	1
Paragonimiasis	0	1	0	1

Prognostic factors were examined for the length of the symptoms, the presence of hydrocephalus, the degree of surgical removal of the tumour, the surgical technique, the size, the location, and the grade of the tumour (Table 5). Despite the study's short sample size, it appeared that individuals with high grade tumours and symptom duration of less than one month had a bad prognosis. On the other hand, patients with lateral ventricle tumours had generally positive prognoses.

Table 5: Analysis of prognostic factors

	No. of patients	Good outcome (%)	Poor outcome (%)	p-value
Symptom duration	15			
< 1 month	7	4(57.1)	3(42.9)	
> 1 month	8	7(87.5)	1(12.5)	0.231
Types of removal	15			
gross total resection	12	9(75.0)	3(25.0)	
subtotal resection	3	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	0.694
Preoperative	15			
present	10	8(80.0)	2(20.0)	
absent	5	3(60.0)	2(40.0)	0.425
Approaches	12			
transcortical	8	7(87.5)	1(12.5)	
transcallosal	4	3(75.0)	1(25.0)	0.478

Location	15			
lateral	6	6(100.0)	0(0.0)	
third	7	4(57.1)	3(42.9)	
fourth	2	1(50.0)	1(50.0)	0.084
Histologic grade	15			
high grade	4	2(50.0)	2(50.0)	
low grade	11	9(81.8)	2(18.2)	0.155

Discussion

Only 3% to 10% of all cerebral neoplasms are intraventricular tumours, which are uncommon CNS masses [8]. According to Jelinek *et al* [6] categorising patients' ages, tumour sites, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging results can all aid in the differential diagnosis of the many types of lateral ventricle tumours. With the exception of two cases of meningioma in the trigone of the lateral ventricle, authors were only able to notice the challenges in the differential diagnosis of ventricular malignancies from MRI results. Additionally, it was challenging to identify the ventricular tumours' predisposing regions. It was presumably caused by the study's limited sample size and the diverse pathophysiology of the tumours. As a result, a longer study should be conducted for results that can be confirmed.

Increased intracranial pressure and direct pressure on the surrounding brain structures are the main causes of the clinical symptoms caused by tumors [8,13]. The majority of intraventricular tumours are benign or low grade [11]. Unless the lesion is positioned in a location where it interferes with CSF circulation early on [8,13] tumours frequently develop slowly and reach a sizeable size before they exhibit symptoms. In addition, pressure from the tumour on the brain parenchyma can cause seizure attack, motor and sensory disruption, limited vision field, difficulties urinating, and gait disturbance. The main clinical symptoms in the instance of the author were headache, altered

consciousness, and vomiting brought on by elevated intracranial pressure. Some patients displayed visual field loss, seizure, gait, and memory problems.

Patients with tumours in the third ventricle demonstrated abrupt loss of consciousness, while all patients with tumours in the lateral ventricle displayed severe headache for several months. Statistics showed that there was a variation in the clinical presentation depending on the location of the tumour ($p=0.012$).

This finding suggested that a tumour in the third ventricle may quickly impede the CSF channel, increasing intracranial pressure. The location of the tumour, rather than its size or clinical diagnosis, is more crucial in the development of hydrocephalus [7]. In the author's study, 85% of patients with tumours in the third ventricle, 50% of patients with tumours in the lateral ventricle, and 50% of patients with tumours in the fourth ventricle also had hydrocephalus. However, statistical analysis found that the differences in hydrocephalus development were unreliable ($p > 0.05$).

The ventricular tumour is an uncharacteristically diverse collection of pathologic abnormalities. According to a study on ventricular tumours in Japan, common histopathologies included craniopharyngioma, astrocytoma, germinoma, pituitary adenoma, malignant astrocytoma, glioblastoma, ependymoma, oligodendroglioma, malignant lymphoma,

teratoma, and pineoblastoma in the third ventricle Meningioma, hemangioblastoma, anaplastic astrocytoma, oligodendroglioma, central neurocytoma, choroid plexus papilloma, cavernous hemangioma, giant cell astrocytoma, ependymoma, subependymoma, malignant lymphoma, and teratoma were among the ventricular tumours. Additionally, the histopathology of the author's cases varied, and these included central neurocytoma, germinoma, meningioma, subependymal giant cell astrocytoma, chordoid astrocytoma, paraganglioma, pilocytic astrocytoma, metastatic tumour, anaplastic astrocytoma, primitive neuroectodermal tumour, atypical teratoid- Four of the 15 patients in the histological investigation had high grade tumours. In two patients, the tumours were found in the third ventricle, and in two others, in the fourth ventricle. The third and fourth ventricles were the predisposing locations of the high grade tumours, despite the fact that it was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Finding the optimum surgical route and assessing the nearby anatomical features are the goals of surgical planning for malignancies in the ventricle. Additionally, the position and size of the tumour, the size of the ventricles, the distribution of the arteries, any neurological abnormalities, and the position of the dominant cerebral hemisphere must all be taken into account. Numerous neurosurgeons have discussed numerous surgical methods since Dandy [3,4] first published the transcortical and transcallosal procedures to the third and lateral ventricular tumours in the 1930s.

In five of the six patients with lateral ventricle tumours and one patient with a transcallosal approach, the tumour was effectively removed. Patients with ventriculomegaly may benefit most from a transcortical approach in general [11].

Despite the lack of ventriculomegaly, authors were nonetheless able to successfully remove malignancies from the frontal horn in two cases and the atrium in one case using a transcortical technique.

One patient underwent subtotal removal by a transcortical method, and another underwent gross complete removal through a transcallosal approach in patients whose lateral ventricle tumours extended to the corpus callosum and the opposite lateral ventricle. In individuals whose malignancies in the lateral ventricle extended contralaterally and superiorly to the ventricle, authors favoured the transcallosal technique.

Despite the fact that numerous studies have found a significant incidence of postoperative seizures following transcortical approaches [1] authors were able to prevent these seizures by making a small cortical incision and not using the retractors.

Three patients had their cancers removed by a transcortical transforaminal technique, three through a transcallosal interforaminal route, and one patient had their malignancies removed through a subfrontal trans-lamina terminalis approach. For the excision of ventricular tumours, the transcallosal technique developed by Dandy [3] and supported by Shucart and Stein [14] appears to provide a number of benefits. When locating intraventricular malignancies, this method offers surgeons more orienting anatomical features than the transcortical approach [11] Although Jeeves *et al* [5] discovered some impairment in the transfer of tactile information, it does not need the ablation of cortical tissue, may be employed independently of ventricular size, and appears not to have long-lasting neurological or behavioural sequelae [1,16].

It is important to pay attention during the transcallosal approach to prevent sagittal sinus injury or injury to the veins that drain the sagittal sinus from causing venous

infarction or other severe neurologic consequences. In order to prevent postoperative venous infarction and other neurological problems, authors did not employ the retractors to protect the big cortical veins throughout the procedure, especially those draining into the sagittal sinus.

The callosal incision should be made in accordance with normal anatomy to minimise complications after callosotomy. To protect the indusium griseum, it's crucial to separate the corpus callosum precisely at the midline. Due to the third ventricle's potential distortion, it must also be aware of the third ventricle's spatial orientation.

Due to the study group's modest size ($p > 0.05$), the variations in postoperative outcomes according to the approach approaches did not appear to be statistically significant.

The transvermian and telovelar methods are the two surgical techniques most frequently used to access the fourth ventricle [9,12,15].

In the author's cases, a transvermian technique was used to remove all of the malignancies from the fourth ventricle. Even though the transvermian method has significant limitations in reaching the lateral recess, the authors were able to successfully resect the tumours with little vermian retraction and prevent caudal vermian syndrome. Due to the use of a single approach in this study, authors were unable to compare the differences in postoperative outcomes between various approach methods to the fourth ventricle.

Extraventricular drainage was carried out by authors in eight patients with preoperative hydrocephalus, and it was kept in place for a few days after surgery. Shunting or extraventricular drainage may be used to treat hydrocephalus that developed before to and after surgery. With preoperative

extraventricular drainage and maintenance of this drainage postoperatively, authors could reduce the risk of sustaining hydrocephalus. Not all patients required a shunt procedure. Shunt surgery is necessary in patients who develop postoperative hydrocephalus, though.

73% of individuals who had tumours removed overall had positive postoperative results (GOS 4, 5). In their series, Lee *et al.* [8] reported a good postsurgical outcome of 75.6% and identified the variables associated with a poor outcome, such as an abrupt onset of symptoms, hydrocephalus prior to surgery, partial tumour resection, postoperative intracranial haemorrhage, persistent hydrocephalus, and newly developed seizures. In our analysis, the placement of the tumour, particularly in the lateral ventricle, was associated with a favourable surgical result.

A rapid start of symptoms and malignant histological findings were associated with a bad prognosis. Malignant tumours had a bad prognosis since there was a high likelihood that the tumours would return. Even after complete removal of malignant tumours, ongoing monitoring is thought to be necessary.

By using several approaches, we were unable to detect any changes in prognosis. Each strategy has benefits and drawbacks.

If we accurately comprehend each surgical technique and have a solid understanding of surgical anatomy and its variations, we can successfully complete surgery without experiencing any major postoperative difficulties.

Conclusion

Depending on where they are located and the various histopathologic features, ventricular tumours manifest clinically in different ways. Despite a lack of statistical dependability, postoperative prognosis was influenced by

the tumor's location, the length of its symptoms, the presence of hydrocephalus, and the pathology of the tumour.

Depending on how the tumours were approached, the results were the same. In order to prevent neurological consequences, it was also required to be informed of the numerous approach techniques to the tumours and the anatomy around the ventricle.

Additionally, additional research is required to compile the data of the case for statistical reliability.

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